

PERFORMANCE AND WORK QUALITY OF THE CHAFF COLLECTION IN SWEDEN: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT: Grain chaff could provide 54.8 Mt of additional annual potential biomass in Europe. In the framework of the AGROinLOG H2020 Project, the chaff collection system developed by Thierart company was tested in Sweden to evaluate the amount of biomass collectible, the harvesting losses and performance, and the economic feasibility of the system. Such system allows to collect the chaff separately onto a trailer. The total residual biomass increased by 0.84 t ha⁻¹ without negatively affecting the performance of the combine.

Keywords: biomass; bioenergy; straw; combine harvester; chaff; by-product

1 INTRODUCTION

In Europe the extensive cultivation of cereals provides both food and residual biomass. Among them, straw has been used for century as natural bedding for feedstock but recently, the interest in that material as source of bioenergy has increased. This encourages farmers and contractors to collect as much residual biomass as possible from wheat crops, by also including the lightest part it like the chaff. Chaff is commonly defined as the by-product of cereal harvest comprehensive of glumes, hulls, short straw, damaged kernels and weed seeds. During threshing, the chaff fraction sieved by the cleaning shoe underneath the straw walkers is blown to the rear part of the combine harvester (Craessaerts, Saeys, Missotten, & De Baerdemaeker, 2010). Considering a mean value of chaff to grain ratio of 0.17 (McCartney, Block, Dubeski, & Ohama, 2006) and an annual wheat and spelt (*Triticum* spp., L.) production of 138 Mt [1], more than 23 Mt of chaff is available and harvestable in Europe. Therefore, chaff could represents a valid source of biomass that is not currently exploited mainly because the harvesting combines are not commonly equipped with specific devices capable to separate it efficiently from the straw. So far, the collection of chaff is delimited to the contribution of weed seeds removal, especially appreciated in organic farming [2,3]. In this case, the chaff is either windrowed laterally to the straw swath or accumulated in hips on the ground and burned. However, this technique has the main drawbacks to contribute to the greenhouse effect and waste valuable biomass. Considering the low heating value (LHV) of 15.1 MJ kg⁻¹[4] and low nutrient content [5], the collection of chaff can increase the total biomass collected without significant reduction in the soil fertility. The energetic aspect of chaff collection is becoming more and more relevant. In fact, the European policy for energy production encourages the exploitation of biomass produced as residual instead of relying on energy crops plantation [6]. Furthermore, the current availability of bio-resources is not sufficient to meet the future energy needs and to respond to the new targets of EU 2030 framework for climate and energy policies [7,8]. In this scenario, it is crucial to foster the

exploitation biomass resources, like the residues produced in agricultural crops, that are not currently included [9]. In the framework of the AGROinLOG H2020 Project, a specific test was performed in Sweden in 2019 in order to evaluate the possibility to collect the chaff simultaneously to the harvesting of the wheat grains. A conventional combine harvester was equipped with the twin-stage turbine technology developed by Thierart company which collected the chaff directly from the exit of the cleaning shoe of the combine and blew it onto a towed trailer. Performance, biomass losses and operating costs of the machines involved were also evaluated.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Field site and experimental design

The test was performed at Lilla Boslin (Halland region, Sweden) (56°35'48"N 12°57'33"E) during the 35th week of 2019. An homogeneous area of 1.5 ha⁻¹ was preliminary selected. The surrounding wheat was harvested and the whole biomass removed in order to avoid edge effects. The remaining portion of the field was then divided in three blocks 0.5 ha⁻¹ each. Equipment A combine harvester New Holland TX68 with conventional cleaning shoe was used to perform the test. The header measured 7.27 m in width and it was specifically dedicated for cereal harvesting. The machine is driven by 209 kW diesel engine and the chassis is comprehensive of a dedicated hitch for trailer towing. The combine harvester was also equipped with auxiliary hydraulic connections for controlling the movements of the trailer while discharging the chaff. The trailer used was a single-axed wagon with a pivoted drawbar directly connected to the hitch of the combine (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The conventional combine harvester equipped with the twin-stage turbine for the collection of the chaff. The towed wagon receive the chaff via the pipe.

The loading capacity of the trailer was 6 m^3 . The upper part of the trailer was closed with a thick plastic film in order to prevent accidental loss of chaff due to wind interference.

2.2 Twin stage turbine technology

The device for the chaff recovery was installed at the end of the cleaning shoe of the combine harvester. As shown in Figure 1, the device is made of a tank that receives the chaff from the cleaning shoe, within it there is a steal-made screw that delivers the chaff to the two stage turbine which, in turn, blows it through the outlet. Here, a PVC pipe is connected in order to permit the discharge of the chaff either on the swath or onto the trailer. The screw and the twin-stage turbine are driven by the dedicated hydraulic system.

Figure 2: Device developed by Thierart for chaff recovery: (1) two stages turbine; (2) specific support for the installation; (3) access hatch to the screw for inspection.

According to the Company [11], the device requires a minimum of 45 l min^{-1} of hydraulic oil flow rate to work properly and the cutting bar of the combine harvester should not exceed 5.5 m in width

2.3 Baler and tractor

The straw produced during the harvesting was baled using a roto baler John Deere 550 towed by a tractor John Deere 6830. The compression chamber of the baler was completely empty at the beginning of each plot, whereas the tank of the tractor was filled with fuel before the start for fuel consumption evaluation. Consequently, at the end the machine was forced to close the bale even if undersized. This last one was not included in the calculation of the mean weight of the bales.

2.4 Performance of the machines

The performance of the machines were evaluated through the study of the working times, performed according to the *Comité International d'Organisation*

Scientifique du Travail en Agriculture (CIOSTA) methodology and the recommendations from the Italian Society of Agricultural Engineering (A.I.I.A.) 3A R1 [12] and the evaluation of the field speed allowed the determination of the Theoretical Field Capacity (TFC) (ha h^{-1}), the Effective Field Capacity (EFC) (ha h^{-1}), and the Field Efficiency (FE) (%). Material Capacity (MC) (t ha^{-1}) was calculated by taking into account the yield of the plots referred to hectare. Gathered data were used to define the performance of the machines and the operative costs.

2.5 Pre-harvest and post-harvest test and theoretical biomass assessment for loss calculation

Before the harvesting, the whole plants of 10 samples areas of 1 m^2 each randomly chosen were hand harvested from the ground level. Culms and spikes were weighed separately. Successively, all spikes and a representative sample of culms were put in sealed bags and shipped to the laboratory of CREA for further measurements, as: theoretical yield of grain and chaff, dry weight and humidity content. In the laboratory, by using a stationary thresher (PLOT 2375 Thresher, Cicoria Company, San Gervasio, Italy), kernels were first separated in from the rest of the spikes (rachis, lemma, glumes and palea). Dry weight and humidity content of culms, kernels and chaff was assessed according to the EN ISO 18134-2:2017[13]. After baling, all bales produced within the plots were weighed singularly for total biomass baled assessment and average fresh weight of the bales. The trailer towed by the combine harvester was weighted empty (tare) and full at the end of each plot (gross weight) on the *in-situ* scale. The net weight of the chaff collected was calculated as the difference between the gross weight and tare.

Losses of biomass were assessed for stubbles, straw and chaff. By knowing the cutting height of the combine header, stubbles were reconstructed in the laboratory by cutting the basal part of culms previously harvested for pre-harvest analysis. The so stubble obtained, were weighted for fresh weight and dried in a ventilated oven at $105 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until constant weight. Straw and chaff loss were determined as difference between the theoretical biomass available derived from the pre-harvest analysis and the effective biomass weighted at the end of the test.

2.6 Cost analysis

In the economic analysis the following parameters have been taken into account: purchase and operating costs that were provided by the contractor via *vis-a-vis* interview, performance of the machines derived from the field tests as primary data, and standard values reported in CRPA methodology [12]. Hourly costs of machines were calculated according to [14,15] on the basis of the market value of the agricultural machinery. The prices of the machines have been discounted to 2019 applying the Lending Rate of 3 % provided by Banca d' Italia Institute [16].

Table I: Economic allocation for the cost analysis of grain, straw and chaff harvesting using a combine equipped with a twin-stage turbine technology for collecting the loose chaff onto a towed trailer

Wheat fraction	Market price [€ t ⁻¹]	Yield [t ha ⁻¹]	Revenue [€ ha ⁻¹]	Economic allocation	
				Harvesting [%]	Baling [%]
Grain	198.5 ¹	9.83	1951.26	89.2	0.0
Straw	50 ¹	3.88	194	8.9	100.0
Chaff	50 ¹	0.84	42	1.9	0.0
<i>Total</i>			<i>2187.26</i>	<i>100.0</i>	<i>100.0</i>

¹: prices retrieved from Camera di Commercio di Modena (2019)

2.7 Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis was performed in order to discriminate the differences among the treatments of the same year. All data were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the R 3.6.1 software to separate statistically different means.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of pre-harvesting highlighted that the total aboveground biomass was 18.8 t ha⁻¹. Chaff, corresponded to 1.84 t ha⁻¹. The moisture content for chaff was equal to 9.0% (± 3.5). After the harvesting, the different fractions of biomass collected are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Effective tons of fresh biomass collected.

In Table II data about the performance of the combine and of the baler are given to the reader. As it is possible to notice there is a substantial difference, for what concerning the combine, between the theoretical field capacity (TFC) and the effective field capacity (EFC). Such differences are linked to the time needed for unloading the wagon. About baling the results were similar to similar previous studies [10,18].

Table II: Performance of the machine involved in the supply chain of wheat grain, straw and chaff.

Machine	T.F.C. [ha h ⁻¹]	E.F.C. [ha h ⁻¹]	F.E. [%]	Material capacity	
				[t _{grain} h ⁻¹]	[t _{residue} h ⁻¹]
Combine harvester	2.17 \pm 0.20	1.02 \pm 0.18	0.47 \pm 0.05	9.87 \pm 0.82	0.85 \pm 0.05
Baler	2.86 \pm 0.43	1.92 \pm 0.09	0.68 \pm 0.07		7.47 \pm 0.85

Data on biomass losses during harvesting are given in Table III. For what concerning straw the total amount present on the field was 8.02 t ha⁻¹ while the baled straw

was equal to 3.88 t ha⁻¹ with a loss of about 52% linked to the low pick-up width of the baler which did not allow for the collection of the overall straw swath.

Table III: fresh biomass outputs from wheat crop, due to the use of a twin-stage Turbine for chaff collection.

Machine	Yield			
	Grain [t ha ⁻¹]	Residue [t ha ⁻¹]	Bale Density [kg m ⁻³]	Chaff Bulk Density [kg m ⁻³]
Combine	9.83 \pm 1.26	0.84 \pm 0.12	-	41.75 \pm 3.30
Baler	-	3.88 \pm 0.06	76.78 \pm 1.83	-

Focusing on cost analysis results are given to the reader in Table IV.

Table IV: Costs for unit of time, surface and ton of biomass processed. G: grain, S: straw, C: chaff.

	Unit	G	S	C	Total Costs
Market price	[€ t ⁻¹]	198.5	50	50	
Yield	[t ha ⁻¹]	9.83	3.88	0.84	
Cost allocation	[%]	89%	9%	2%	100%
Combine harvester +	[€ h ⁻¹]	123.01	12.23	2.65	137.89
Twin stage turbine + Wagon	[€ ha ⁻¹]	120.6	11.99	2.6	135.18
Cost allocation	[€ t ⁻¹]	12.27	3.09	3.09	18.45
Baling	[%]	0%	100%	0%	100%
Tractor + Baler	[€ h ⁻¹]		116.85		116.85
	[€ ha ⁻¹]		60.86		60.86
	[€ t ⁻¹]		15.69		15.69
Total cost of the harvesting system	[€ h ⁻¹]	123.01	129.08	2.65	254.74
	[€ ha ⁻¹]	120.6	72.85	2.6	196.04
	[€ t ⁻¹]	12.27	18.78	3.09	

According to the obtained results on cost analysis with chaff collection onto a trailer with Thierart turbine system it is possible to obtain an extra gain of 39.40 € ha⁻¹.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Few experiences with the collection of chaff are present in the literature as well as little information is available regarding the available quantities, losses, and collection costs. For this reason, this work is an important piece because it fills a gap in the collection phase of a residual.

Through the test it was possible to understand the necessary measures to reduce the loss of product during collection, and the performance of a system based on both the separate collection of the chaff on trailer towed by the combine, and the joined collection of straw and chaff, and the associated costs.

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